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THE TRADITIONAL DISEASE NAMES IN THE ENGLISH, RUSSIAN AND UZBEK
LANGUAGES WITH THE SAME SEMANTIC ORIGIN

INGLIZ, RUS VA O'ZBEK TILLARIDAGI SEMANTIK KELIB CHIQISHI BIRHIL BO'LGAN
XALQ ORASIDAGI KASALLIK NOMLARI

ТРАДИЦИОННЫЕ НАЗВАНИЯ БОЛЕЗНЕЙ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ, РУССКОМ И
УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ С ПОХОЖИМ СЕМАНТИЧЕСКИМ ПРОИСХОЖДЕНИЕМ

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Abstract. Words expressing the names of diseases have a special place in the language and speech of the people of the world. They are valuable in that they reflect the unique way of thinking, worldview, cultural and spiritual concepts, life experiences and traditions of each nation. Being located in different parts of the world, some nations created the same traditional names for disease. This is important and necessary to distinguish the specific features of their lexical-semantic, methodological-functional use in oral and written speech. The English, Russian and Uzbek languages have been developing independently and belong to different language branches. However, in these languages there are traditional disease names the origins of which have the same meaning. This article presents the folk disease names with the same semantic origin in the English, Russian, and Uzbek languages.

Key words: disease, diagnose, semantics, origin, language family, folk names

Annotatsiya. Kasallik nomlarini ifodalovchi so'zlar dunyo xalqlari tili va nutqida alohida o'rin tutadi. Ular har bir xalqning o'ziga xos tafakkuri, dunyoqarashi, madaniy-ma'naviy g'oyalari, hayotiy tajribasi va an'analarini o'zida aks ettirgani bilan qimmatlidir. Dunyoning turli burchaklarida bo'lgan ba'zi xalqlar kasalliklar uchun bir xil an'anaviy nomlarni yaratdilar. Ushbu tillardagi og'zaki va yozma nutqda leksik-semantik, uslubiy va funksional qo'llanish xususiyatlarini farqlash muhim va zarurdir. Ingliz, rus va o'zbek tillari mustaqil rivojlanib, turli til oilalariga kiradi. Biroq, bu tillarda kelib chiqishi bir xil ma'noga ega bo'lgan xalq kasallik nomlari mavjuddir. Ushbu maqolada ingliz, rus va o'zbek tillarida semantik kelib chiqishiga o'xshash xalq orasida tarqalgan kasalliklarning nomlari keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: kasallik, tashxis, semantika, kelib chiqishi, til oilasi, xalq orasidagi nomlar.

Аннотация. Слова, выражающие названия болезней, занимают особое место в языке и речи народов мира. Они ценны тем, что отражают уникальный образ мышления, мировоззрение, культурные и духовные представления, жизненный опыт и традиции каждого народа. Находясь в разных частях света, некоторые народы создали для болезней одни и те же традиционные названия. Это важно и необходимо, чтобы различать особенности их лексико-семантического, методологически-функционального использования в устной и письменной речи. Английский, русский и узбекский языки развивались независимо и относятся к разным языковым ветвям. Однако в этих языках существуют традиционные названия болезней, происхождение которых имеет одно и то же значение. В данной статье представлены сходные по смысловому происхождению народные названия болезней в английском, русском и узбекском языках.

Ключевые слова: болезнь, диагностика, семантика, происхождение, языковая семья, народные имена.

Introduction. Humanity has always been worried about problems with maintaining health, prolonging life, diagnosing diseases and treating them. Thus, medical lexis plays an important role

in lexicology of all languages. Disease names can reveal a lot of information about the history of medicine.

Throughout history, the names given to diseases have been influenced by different things in different places and at different times, leading to a very wide array of naming practices and preferences. The disease names have usually been named after the place they were first encountered (Ebola virus, Chinese flu, Spanish flu), after common animal vectors (monkeypox, swine flu), or after doctors or researchers (Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease, Charcot-Marie-Tooth disease, Lou Gehrig's disease Alzheimer's disease and Parkinson's disease) who first documented them. However, the folk names often originated relying on the characteristics of the diseases.

Surprisingly, through the history some disease names in different nations got the names with the same semantic origin. Therefore, this work aims to identify the semantic similarities in the folk names of diseases in the English, Russian and Uzbek languages

Literature review. A formal word “disease” in the English language has synonyms such as bug, malady, ailment, infirmity and etc. The Russian translation of the word “illness” “болезнь” has formal and informal alternatives such as недуг, немощь, скорбь, болеть, хворь and хворобой (1).

National medicine has existed since ancient times among many people. Medical prescriptions, names of diseases and other concepts were passed down from generation to generation, sometimes supplemented by borrowings. Since ancient times nations had their own medical books. Importantly, European science did not exert any influence on these ancient books (Ergasheva, 2022). The texts of folk herbalists and healers differ in many ways from their "scientific" counterparts. Differences are noticeable in such parameters as the language of presentation, the structure of manuscripts, the description of the recipe and functions of plants, diseases, design and content.

It must also be mentioned that English, Uzbek and Russian are typologically and genetically diverse languages. English and Russian belong to the Germanic and Slavic groups of the Indo-European language family. Uzbek belongs to the Turkic group of languages of the Altaic language family (Saloydinova, 2022). Despite the distance and origin, there are still the similarities in the origin of the folk disease names.

The origin of terms that we know today are often related to older ideas about the cause of diseases or to ideas about disease symptoms manifested. It is noteworthy that in the colloquial language the names of diseases are often not determined by the internal reason that causes it. But, people name them according to what they see, feel and some features which disfigure the appearance of people. In other words, diseases acquire their names according to their symptoms and state of a sick person that has external manifestation (e.g. jaundice, roseola, chicken pox), the resemblance of an illness to something (cancer), the period when a disease appears (monthlies), part of the body where they appear (горлянка^ even through the thing that heal a disease (эшак эми). These words are archaic and are stated in folklore texts. Moreover, it is possible to find them in the speech of older rural population.

Research methodology. 50 folk disease names were taken from Uzbek anatomical dictionaries. Their English and Russian folk alternative were found. Semantic and comparative analysis were used in the research.

Results and discussion. Out of 50 folk names 5 of them were found to have the same semantic origin in the three given languages. The following are these diseases.

Roseola is a condition of young children in which a fever lasting for three or four days is followed by a rose-colored rash. Traditionally, it is used for what we now call infantum. This term is known since early 19th century and is derived from Latin word roseus meaning rose-colored (2). In Uzbek the disease, which is called қизамиқ, was in use even in the ancient Turkish language with the same meaning and derived from the verb қън meaning turning red (Рахматуллаев, 2000). Краснуха or красуха, the Russian translation of roseola, is also alludes to red color (Фасмер, 1981).

Icterus is named in spoken language as **jaundice**, which came from an old French word jaundice meaning yellowness, due to yellowish pigmentation on skin and eyes (2). In the Russian colloquial language the illness is known as желтуха. The name was constructed on the basis of the word желтый which itself means yellow (Фасмер, 1981). In the Uzbek spoken language the ailment is called сариқ and means yellow as well (Рахматуллаев, 2000).

Urticaria or **nettle-rash** is a rash of round, red welts on the skin that get itchy intensely, sometimes with dangerous swelling, caused by an allergic reaction, typically to specific foods. The term has been known since late 18th century and is derived from a Latin word “urtica” which means nettle and “urere” burn[5]. In Russian this disease is called as крапивница and constructed on the basis of the word крапива, which means nettle[4].

Ветрянка is an infectious disease causing a mild fever and a rash of itchy inflamed blisters. The term is derived from the word ветер meaning wind. The origin of the name reveals the idea that the disease is contagious and can be transmitted easily through air (Фасмер, 1981). In English the disease is named chicken pox, due to its resemblance to chick peaks. However, in the German language the name of the disorder has a similar origin as it has in Russian, Windpokken.

A sudden stopping of the breath with a cough like sound is named as **hiccup** (Hornby). Only in the 11th century people did begin to use hiccup, closely allied to the Danish hikke and the Dutch hikke. The term is derived from the sound hic that is accompanied with this condition (Hornby). The Russian alternative of the term is икание, which is also onomatopoeic word and constructed from the sound К (Фасмер, 1981). In Uzbek the state is known as хикичок and this word, as well as in other languages, is derived from the sound хик which characterizes this condition (Рахматуллаев, 2000).

From the findings above we can conclude that the folk names mostly originates relying on the description of disease. Featuring the same character of the disease resulted in the origination of the traditional disease names with the same semantic origin in the languages that are remote from each other and come from various language families.

Conclusion. To conclude, although these three languages progressed in their own ways, there are traditional disease terms which were derived from the concepts with the same meaning thus proving that people from different backgrounds may have the same picture of the world.

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